

THE ROLE OF WOMEN - GIRLS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10659014>

Abstract. *In this article, the role of women in society today in the conditions of globalization, the formation of a sound-thinking, scientific, spiritual and moral image of women in Uzbekistan is a necessary condition for the realization of their creative and intellectual potential, and the formation of mature individuals in all aspects. - conditions and opportunities have been created, and on this basis, women have all the opportunities to get a quality education, to acquire a profession, and to be employed, so that they can find their place in life.*

Keywords: *globalization, education, women, women, family, humanity, reform.*

INTRODUCTION

Protecting the rights and interests of women, strengthening their health and, most importantly, creating decent living conditions for them are the main directions of the social sphere. In the effective system of preschool, secondary, secondary and higher education in our country, one of the important directions is to fully ensure the right of women and girls to receive education. Today in Uzbekistan, it is possible to witness that our women and girls are occupying more and more advanced positions in all fields. They make a significant contribution to the development of education, culture and science of our country. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to implement national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030" was adopted. At the same time, within the framework of the implementation of the Fifth Sustainable Development Goal, Uzbekistan has developed nine tasks related to "Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and obligations of all women". According to the mission of the fifth goal, by 2030, it is necessary to eliminate all forms of discrimination against all women, to ensure the full and effective participation of women and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and social life. In addition, this goal includes the implementation of the principles of gender equality in the process of adoption of the State Program at different levels of the state.

The main part: "The issue of women and the family is a decisive factor that determines not only our present, but also our future tomorrow. If we do one favor to women, who are the symbols of kindness and loyalty, the angels of our homes, it will surely be returned as ten favors." Sh.M. Mirziyoyev

As we all know, one of the priority directions of our state's policy is to pay attention and care to the younger generation in Uzbekistan to get a thorough education, acquire a profession, and mature in the spirit of respect for our national traditions and values.

Especially in today's globalization and rapidly changing complex and intense era, protecting the spirituality of our country's youth from various threats, making them understand the essence of the processes taking place in the international arena, having an impartial and independent opinion on these realities, is a correct and acceptable conclusion. public organizations, political parties, whose place and role are increasing in the deepening of democratic reforms in the country in the following years, along with the effective establishment of family-neighborhood-educational institution cooperation in the formation and development of their talents, increasing the activity of other civil society institutions is of urgent importance. Globalization is an ongoing

socio-historical process, and the main factor that shapes it, develops it and affects it to a certain extent is man. By the 21st century, trends of commonality are visible in every direction of human social development, namely scientific and technical revolution, development of sciences, generalization of cultures, information communications, ideological influences. What effect does globalization have on women's lives today, on their spiritual and moral image? In this case, the issues of a woman's place in society, her weight in production, her rights and freedoms, her health, responsibility for the nation's gene pool, and social protection are relevant in every society.

Jean-Jacques Rousseau defines a woman as follows: "The power of a woman lies in her charm." While the woman-family has been fulfilling the duty of a passionate and self-sacrificing guardian, women's participation in social life is accelerating: in the spheres of state administration, production, education, and community health. In modernizing Uzbekistan, it is necessary to increase the intellectual capabilities of women in the field of technology and information communications, to be regularly informed about science, culture and technology news, and to enrich the accumulated experience with new scientific ideas and new technologies. 'a great person who rides. After all, a woman rocks the cradle with one hand and the world with the other. Therefore, the issue of securing the place of women, her freedom and rights in every society is very important. In this, the spiritual and moral maturity of a woman in the society shows the honor of the country and the nation.

Formation of the spiritual and moral image of a woman is an issue at the level of state policy, which requires a detailed study of the Eastern woman, her participation in the family, neighborhood, community and state administration. In this regard, it is important to educate women and guide them in a targeted manner, to teach them a trade, thus to gain their place and respect in the society, to increase their involvement in social and political processes in the country, to form an active citizen's position, and therefore to form legal literacy and political consciousness. A number of tasks have been set for the development of women in the modernizing Uzbekistan, and they are being implemented step by step. That is, the establishment of the state committee for family and women, the introduction of the position of women's activist in each neighborhood, the adoption of the national program for supporting women's education for 2022-2026, the initiative of the President to the public, First of all, the establishment of the "Smart Women" movement, which unites reputable women who can have an educational effect on young people, as well as the establishment of "Women's Councils" in order to find effective solutions to the problems of women in all working groups is the attention given to our girls by our state.

On February 26, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, as a vivid expression of the thoughts of solving the problems of women and providing them with social support, "Encouraging women who want to get a higher education, who have the ability and knowledge, but due to fate, could not achieve their dream" system has been implemented. In other words, covering the contract fee of needy girls who have lost one of their parents, single women without a breadwinner at the expense of the governorship and the higher educational institution is also an encouragement of our women by our state. Of course, this consideration and opportunity is for our girls. Previously, there were no such opportunities. Now there is a chance. In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, the widespread involvement of women in scientific research and innovation activities is gaining urgent importance.

Therefore, on the one hand, to strengthen the activity of women and girls of our country in science at the international level, on the other hand, it is extremely necessary to achieve gender equality in the fields of education and science. Because, in fact, if a woman is educated, her

children will be intelligent and capable. More importantly, if a woman is knowledgeable, the nation will be knowledgeable. Almost half of the population of our country - 17 million - are women. In this sense, as a result of the creation of great opportunities for girls to get a quality education, get a profession, and be employed, it is noteworthy that women make up half of the students today.

At the same time, since last year, the educational opportunities of girls in need of social protection have been expanded and state grants of 4% have been allocated to higher education institutions.

According to the Information Service of the Ministry of Innovative Development, the competition of initiative scientific projects "Women Scientists" announced by the Ministry in (2020) is aimed at strengthening the position of women in science. About 3,000 women are conducting research in scientific institutes under the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. In this regard, it is very important that a number of laws, state programs and practical mechanisms aimed at increasing the share of women in the field of science have been developed and widely implemented in our country within the framework of the "Strategy of Actions". President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the UN Human Rights Council on February 22 of this year It is no coincidence that he put forward new initiatives on gender equality policy in his historic speech at the 46th session. By the way, our President also proposed to establish a separate state award in Uzbekistan to encourage selfless services of women to the state and society, achievements in their fields. In accordance with the resolution 70/212 of the UN General Assembly, adopted on December 22, 2015, February 11 is declared as the International Day of Women in the Field of Science.

Conclusion: In other words, the respect for women in our country and the fact that the door of opportunities has been opened, the formation of the spiritual and moral image of our women, the fact that our country has all the opportunities for our modern and learned women to be scientists who educate our future successors, and how many more incentives What is being carried out is a manifestation of the fulfillment of our biggest dreams of women, and this will certainly only lead to success.

REFERENCES

1. Sh. Mirziyoyev. "Increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work and on raising the development of the industry to a new level" No. PQ-3160 numerical decision. July 28, 2017.
2. Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the ceremony dedicated to the International Women's Day. // People's word, March 8, 2021.
3. Hakimova M., Musahanova G. 2019. Professional pedagogy. T. TDIU, 306 p.
4. Musakhanova G. Design and research method as an innovative approach aimed at the development of organizational abilities of students in the process of independent work. Current research journal of pedagogy. 2021. T.2. #09. p. 110-
5. M. Mukhlibayev. —Ways of forming an integrative ecological culture of young people in the era of globalization|| —Quality education and interdisciplinary approach: problems, solutions and cooperation|| May 25-26, 2023
6. A woman is the guardian of the family building. "Academic Research in Educational Sciences" (Uzbekistan), 2021 No. 2(2), 101-106- p
7. Resolution of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. SQ-297-IV of May 28, 2021 "On approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030"

8. Gaffarova G.G., Abdullayeva M.N. (2020). The cognitive system of Sufism in the prism of modern philosophy. Academic research in educational sciences. #3.
9. Gaffarova, Gulchehra G'ulamzhanovna. (2020). Theory of autopoiesis in cognitive process. Scientific-practical research in Uzbekistan: materials of the 16th multidisciplinary distance scientific online conference on the scale of the republic. 193-196.
10. G.G. Gaffarova, (2020). Strategy of activity and systematic approach. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. London, United Kingdom, 24, Issue-5, May. - 6645-6651.